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ECCENTRIC PREGNANCY AND UTERINE ANOMALIES – A RARE CASES OF OBSTETRICAL HEMORRHAGE

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ABSTRACT

Obstetric hemorrhage is still one of the urgent problems of modern obstetrics. Obstetric hemorrhage is one of the leading causes of maternal death in Uzbekistan, with maternal mortality rate of 1 case per 1000 births from postpartum hemorrhage. According to the 1st and 2nd reports of the "Confidential analysis of cases of maternal deaths" in Uzbekistan, one of the main untapped opportunities for bleeding prevention is the underestimation of risk factors for hemorrhage. **The objective of the research** was to provide a description of 3 cases of eccentric pregnancy and the possibility of preventing massive hemorrhage. **Material and methods of research.** This article deals with description of 3 clinical cases of obstetric hemorrhage as a result of congenital anomalies of the uterus and atypical implantation of the embryo, as well as an analysis of current information on this problem. **Results:** we give a description of 3 rare cases, of which two – cornual pregnancies and one angular pregnancy. All cases were complicated by profuse hemorrhage. One primigravida had a fatal rupture of the rudimentary horn. **Conclusion.** Eccentric pregnancy is still a little-known condition in modern obstetrics with life-threatening complications in pregnant women, which requires careful selection of such pregnant women through screening at early gestational ages and closer monitoring and timely subsequent delivery.

Key words: obstetric hemorrhage, uterine anomalies, eccentric pregnancy, angular pregnancy, cornual pregnancy.

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ЭКСЦЕНТРИЧНАЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТЬ И АНОМАЛИИ МАТКИ – РЕДКИЕ ПРИЧИНЫ АКУШЕРСКИХ КРОВОТЕЧЕНИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Акушерские кровотечения все еще остаются одной из актуальных проблем современного акушерства и являются одной из ведущих причин материнской смертности в Узбекистане. По данным 1-го и 2-го отчетов «Конфиденциального исследования случаев материнской смертности» в Узбекистане одним из основных неиспользованных возможностей для профилактики акушерских кровотечений является недоучет факторов риска на кровотечение. **Цель.** Представить описание случаев эксцентричной беременности и возможности предотвращения массивных кровопотерь. **Материал и методы.** В данной статье описаны 3 клинических случаев акушерских кровотечений в результате аномалии развития матки и атипичной имплантации эмбриона, а также анализ современной информации о данной проблеме. **Результаты.** Приводим описание 3 редких случаев, из которых в двух - расположение беременности в роге матке (корнуальная беременность) и в одном - в углу матки (ангулярное расположение). Все случаи осложнились обильным кровотечением. У одной первобеременной произошел разрыв рудиментарного рога с летальным исходом. **Вывод.** Эксцентричная беременность все еще остается малоизвестным состоянием в современном акушерстве с угрожающими жизни беременных женщин осложнениями, которое требуют тщательного отбора таких беременных путем скрининга в малых сроках гестации и более пристального наблюдения за ними и своевременным последующим родоразрешением.

Ключевые слова: акушерское кровотечение, аномалия развития матки, эксцентричная беременность, ангулярная беременность, корнуальная беременность.

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ЕКСТСЕНТРИК ХОМИЛАДОРЛИК ВА БАЧАДОН НУҚСОНЛАРИ - АКУШЕРЛИК ҚОН КЕТИШЛАРИНИНГ КАМ УЧРАЙДИГАН САБАБЛАРИ

АННОТАТСИЯ

Akusherlik qon ketishlar hanzugacha zamonaviy akusherlikning dolzarb muammolaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. O'zbekistonda akusherlik qon ketishlar onalar o'limining asosiy sabablaridan biri bo'lib, tug'ruqdan keyingi akusherlik qon ketishlar natijasida kuzatiladigan onalar o'limi har 1000 tugruqdan 1 holatda kuzatiladi. O'zbekistonda "Onalar o'limi holatlarining konfidentsial tahlili"ning 1 va 2-chi hisobotiga ko'ra, akusherlik qon ketishlarning oldini olishning asosiy foydalanilmagan imkoniyatlaridan biri bu qon ketishi xavf omillarini yetarlicha baholamaslikdir. **Tadqiqot maqsadi:** ekstsentrik homiladorlikning 3 holatini hamda kuzatilishi mumkin bo'lgan qon ketishlarni oldini oluvchi imkoniyatlarni taqdim etish. **Tadqiqot materiali va usullari:** mazkur maqolada bachadon tug'ma nuqsoni hamda atipik implantatsiya natijasida kuzatilgan akusherlik qon ketishlarning 3 holati hamda zamonaviy ma'lumotlar tahlili keltirilgan. **Tadqiqot natilasi:** 3-ta kam uchrovchi akusherlik qon ketishlar holatlari, 2 holatda homiladorlik bachadon shoxida joylashgan bo'lib (kornual homiladorlik) 1 holatda homiladorlik bachadon burchagida (angulyar homiladorlik) joylashgan. Barcga holatlar akusherlik qon ketishlar bilan asoratlanib, 1 holatda bachadon shoxining yorilishi natijasida o'lim kuzatilgan. **Xulosa:** ekstsentrik homiladorlik hali ham zamonaviy akusherlikdagi kam o'rganilgan holat bo'lib homilador ayollar hayotiga xavf soluvchi asoratlarga ega. Shuning uchun ham bunday homiladorlar homiladorlikning erta muddatlarida skrining yordamida saralanib keyinchalik nazoratga olinib, o'z vaqtida tug'dirilishi zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: akusherlik qon ketishi, bachadon anomaliyasi, ekstsentrik homiladorlik, angulyar homiladorlik, kornual homiladorlik.

Introduction: Obstetrical hemorrhage still remains as one of three main causes of maternal deaths in the world, and of these postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) accounts for one-quarter, although it is a preventable and treatable complication of childbirth, [6,10]. To date, postpartum hemorrhage is classified according to its causative factors which are divided into 4 groups and referred as "4T", from the first letters of the causes: 1) Tonus: uterine atony (70%), 2) Trauma: injuries to the birth canal/uterus (20%) 3) Tissue: remnants of placental tissue/abnormal implantation of placenta (10%) and 4) Thrombin: coagulation defects (congenital or acquired) (<1%) [14].

According to the 1st and 2nd reports of the "Confidential Study of cases of Maternal Deaths" in Uzbekistan, one of the main untapped opportunities for the prevention of obstetrical hemorrhage is the underestimation of risk factors for obstetrical hemorrhage [14].

Recently, more and more data is being appeared in the literature about congenital uterine anomalies and atypical embryo implantations leading to PPH up to fatal, which require additional interventions, both conservative and surgical. But the available literature data related to the above conditions are very scarce.

Although "angular pregnancy" was described over a century ago by Dr. Howard Kelly as "the implantation of an embryo medial to the uterotubal junction, in the lateral angle of the uterine cavity", it is often confused with "interstitial" and "cornual" pregnancy. [3,7]. The term

"cornual pregnancy" was first introduced by Johnston and Moir in 1952 to describe pregnancy in one of the horns of a bicornuate uterus or in one part of the septate uterus [1]. Unlike interstitial - ectopic pregnancy, "angular" and "cornual" pregnancies are uterine (cavitary) forms of pregnancy. Currently, to describe "angular" and "cornual" pregnancies, Alex R. Finlinson et al. (2020) suggest using the term "eccentric (non-central) pregnancy" [6].

Clinical case #1

Patient F, 29 years old, medical record # 3607/702, was admitted with the diagnosis: "G₂P₁ (0-0-1-0) 34 weeks gestation. Controlled preterm labor. Chronic anemia of moderate degree. On the 2nd day, the pregnant woman complained of sudden pain in the lower abdomen and in the lower back, after which vaginal bleeding started. In ultrasonography placental abruption was diagnosed. With the above indication, the patient was urgently taken for a caesarean section under general anesthesia. Intraoperatively, after delivery of the fetus and placenta and exteriorization of the uterus, a "Bicornuate uterus" was diagnosed with a pregnancy in the right horn - a cornual pregnancy. The left horn of the uterus was of normal size. On examination, extreme thinning of the myometrium up to 1-2 mm and its softness in the area of attachment of the placenta with heavy bleeding was determined. Herewith, the fundus of the horn and more than 2/3 of the surface of its cavity was the site of attachment of the placenta (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Cornual pregnancy (illustration for clinical case No. 1).

x-place of implantation in the right horn of the uterus with a sharp thinning of the myometrium with a wide area.

* - intact left uterine horn with appendages

Clamps were placed on the right uterine artery at the level of the incision of the uterus, as well as on the right uteroovarian ligament to control the hemorrhage (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Clamping the vascular bundles to achieve temporary hemostasis (illustration for clinical case No. 1)

Due to the extreme thinning of myometrium and the wide area, attempts to apply compression sutures did not work, the sutures erupted. The hemorrhage from attachment site continued. To achieve complete hemostasis, was decided to remove the right uterine horn, after which complete hemostasis was achieved. Then the remaining steps of the operation were completed. The patient was discharged home on the 10th day in a satisfactory condition.

Clinical case #2

Patient Z., 28 years old, medical record # 2499, was admitted with a diagnosis: "G₂P₂ (1-0-0-1) 39 weeks gestation. Prior cesarean delivery. Chronic anemia of moderate degree. Obesity II degree. She was scheduled for a repeat cesarean section on the next day. Intraoperatively, after delivery of the fetus and placenta, an angular pregnancy in the right corner of the uterus was diagnosed, with extreme thinning of myometrium up to 2-3 mm with a dome-shaped bulging of the latter at the site of attachment with an area of about 4x7 cm with an anomalous vascularization was identified. Myometrium over the site of attachment was soft (Fig. 3, 4).

Figure 3. Angular pregnancy (illustration for clinical case No. 2). There is an asymmetric enlargement of the uterus with a dome-shaped protrusion of the myometrium in the area of implantation in the right corner of the uterus.

Figure 4. Angular pregnancy (illustration for clinical case No. 2). There is an extreme thinning of the myometrium up to 2-3 mm at the implantation site with hypervascularization.

In the rest of its body uterus was contracted and dense. There was profuse hemorrhage from the attachment site of the placenta. In order to control the hemorrhage, manual compression of the placental attachment site was performed. Then, it was decided to administer additionally 100 mg of Carbetocin. After which, the uterus became more contracted and denser. Hemorrhage from the placental attachment site stopped. There was no need for compression sutures. After that, the remaining steps of the operation were completed. The patient was discharged home on the 5th day in a satisfactory condition.

Discussion: Angular pregnancy is considered a rare and little-known form of uterine pregnancy. Although this condition was first described more than a century ago, according to M.B. Rankin et al. (2014) up to date less than 100 cases of angular pregnancy has been reported in the literature [10].

In 1981 R.P.S. Jansen et al (1981) combined the first reported 39 clinical cases of angular pregnancy into a single systematic review, and reported occurrence of miscarriage in 38.5% cases, uterine rupture in 13.6% cases and only in 28% cases pregnancy terminated with a live birth [12]. Further in 2014 M.B. Rankin et al. (2014) conducted another systematic review with the addition of a further 46 cases (total 85 cases) and according to the authors, the risk of miscarriage was 18% and the risk of uterine rupture was 28%. The authors state that the probability of a live birth was almost the same as in the previous review and accounted 25%, however, in cases in which pregnancies were not terminated and were conducted expectantly, the chances of a live birth increased to 69% [10]. According to Cherie Q. et al. (2018) to date, only 31 cases of expectant management of angular pregnancy with subsequent live birth have been described in the literature [3, 10, 13].

When describing the cases of angular pregnancy, the authors often confused angular pregnancy with cornual and interstitial pregnancies. Therefore, in 1981, Jansen and Elliott conducted a study to clarify these pregnancies. To describe each of these pregnancies, i.e. their location relative to the round ligament of the uterus, they used diagnostic laparoscopy. Angular pregnancy is currently diagnosed using the Janson and Elliot criteria, which include 1) presentation with painful and asymmetric uterine enlargement 2) direct (intraoperative) visualization of lateral uterine distension with lateral displacement of the round ligament of the uterus 3) retained placenta/parts of the placenta in the corner of the uterus [6,8].

The term "cornual pregnancy" was first introduced by Johnston and Moir in 1952. They called a pregnancy "cornual" if implantation of

zygote occurs in one of the horns of the bicornuate uterus, or in one of the lateral parts of the septate or arcuate uterus [3].

For several years in literature, pregnancies with implantation of fertilized egg in one of the upper lateral uterine angles with normal uterine anatomy by various authors was also called as "cornual", which led experts into confusion. Therefore, in 1981, Maher and Grimwade proposed to call "cornual pregnancy" those pregnancies with localization in the upper lateral angle with a normal structure of the uterus [11], which was supported by several authorities [2].

But recently, taking into account the opinions of authoritative world journals in obstetrics and gynecology, the latest editions of "Williams Obstetrics" define "cornual" pregnancies that "... develop in the rudimentary horn of the uterus with Mullerian anomaly" [4].

To date, the management of such pregnancies remains debatable. As mentioned above, according to systematic reviews based on clinical cases, the risks of uterine rupture and spontaneous miscarriage are very high. In these studies, the management of pregnancies was mainly conducted by surgery (at least exploratory laparoscopy) and pregnancy termination. Therefore, the opinions of the authors on the management of such pregnancies differ. So Grant et al. (2017) based on the results of their study - a retrospective analysis of clinical cases with a relatively small number of patients report no cases of uterine rupture [7] and small number of cases does not make it possible to draw a final conclusion.

Recent studies from the University of Missouri provide encouraging data on the expectant management of eccentric pregnancies diagnosed in the first trimester of pregnancy. According to their research, 80% of pregnancies ended in a live birth and no single case of uterine rupture, maternal death, abnormal placentation and hysterectomy was reported. Therefore, recent literature data recommend expectant management when eccentric pregnancies are detected in the first trimester, since outcomes are favorable in most cases. If an eccentric pregnancy is detected at a later term (II or III trimester) and presents with pain or bloody discharge, then the management of such patients requires an individual approach depending on the clinical situation [6].

To date there are two surgical approaches for the treatment of eccentric pregnancies – laparoscopy and laparotomy and usually include resection of horn or hysterectomy. However, in milder cases more conservative approaches are used, such as cornuotomy or medical therapy. The main goal of treatment is to preserve the surrounding myometrium as more as possible.

Conclusion: All of the abovementioned life-threatening complications up to fatal, observed in eccentric pregnancies are probably associated with asymmetric growth of uterine body (limited space) by a growing fetus, which leads to overdistention of the myometrium – an acute thinning of the myometrium up to 1-2 mm in the implantation site. This, in turn, leads to “local” atony of the uterine myometrium which results in atonic hemorrhage and not infrequently in uterine rupture.

Thus, it can be said that eccentric pregnancy is still a little-known condition in modern obstetrics with life-threatening complications, which requires careful selection of such pregnant women by screening at early stages of pregnancy and closer monitoring of them and subsequent delivery. All this will contribute to the prevention and reduction of maternal morbidity and mortality in the future.

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